

Application Deployment Manager Interoperability Guideline

09/06/2026

Abstract

As described in the EOSC Federation Handbook, the federating capability of Application Deployment Management (ADM) will enable EOSC users to easily deploy and/or execute applications seamlessly across one or more Nodes. Researchers can discover application recipes and trigger their deployment or execution on an EOSC Node where suitable resources are available.

This interoperability guideline proposes an API for the automated deployment and execution of applications on the underlying EOSC Nodes provisioned infrastructure, together with a reference implementation of the ADM capability based on the Infrastructure Manager (IM).

EOSC Beyond receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101131875

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Document Description

Document title			
Work Package number 14			
Nature of document	Interoperability Guideline	Dissemination level	Public
Document Status	Final	Version	1.0
Lead Partner	UPV		
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Keyword	Application Deployment, TOSCA, Federation, Allocation, Blueprint		

Revision History

Issue	Date	Description	Author/Reviewer
V 0.1	26/03/2023	Draft version	Miguel Caballer Germán Moltó Levente Farkas
V 0.2	31/03/2023	Revised version	Miguel Caballer Germán Moltó
V 0.3	15/05/2026	Revised version	Miguel Caballer Germán Moltó Levente Farkas
V 1.0	09/06/2026	Final	Miguel Caballer Germán Moltó Alessia Bardi

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1 Intended Audience

The audience for the Guideline for ADM is technical representatives from EOSC Nodes who want to:

- interact with an existing compatible ADM service to dynamically deploy applications in the cloud infrastructure of their own node or in other nodes of the federation.
- offer the ADM capability for their node based on an existing reference implementation.
- develop their own particular ADM service.

2 Description and main features

This interoperability guideline proposes an API and a reference implementation based on the Infrastructure Manager [1] for the automated deployment and execution of services on the underlying EOSC Nodes provisioned infrastructure, enabling the ADM federating capability, as described in the EOSC Federation Handbook [2].

The guideline describes the API specification and annexes the OpenAPI 3.1 YAML specification for the API. It also uses the TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.0, as defined in the OASIS standard, to describe the application blueprints.

Figure 1. Overview of the Application Deployment Management federating capability.

Figure 1 provides a diagram of the ADM federating capability. Nodes that participate in the EOSC federation can offer this capability through a service that implements the ADM standardised API, as defined in this ADM Interoperability Guideline. This API allows users to query for the available resource allocations on an EOSC Node and list the application recipes that can be deployed.

2.1 General overview

The ADM API [3], proposed by the EGI foundation with contributions from Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), follows the OpenAPI 3.1 specification, and its main goals are to:

- Provide a federated way to manage execution environments (“allocations”).
- Expose application blueprints available on nodes, including TOSCA, Ansible, and Helm-based specifications.
- Allow users to deploy workloads using these blueprints on eligible environments.
- Offer pagination, strong typing, and uniform error responses for all endpoints.

All endpoints require OIDC (OpenID Connect) Bearer JWT (JSON Web Tokens) issued by the EOSC AAI.

2.2 Core domain model

2.2.1 Applications (Blueprints)

An application defines what to deploy; the applications are not managed by the user and are obtained from an internal database or from external repositories.

- Unique ID and optional version
- Execution type: VM (Virtual Machine) or container (e.g. Docker)
- Blueprint type: toscas, ansible, or helm
- Metadata (author, license, keywords, repository, helpdesk)
- Publication status and favourite flag

2.2.2 Allocations (Environments)

An Allocation represents where an application can be deployed.

All these three kinds must exist (with a discriminator kind):

1. EoscNodeEnvironment
2. OpenStackEnvironment
3. KubernetesEnvironment

EOSC environments add quotas (CPU/GPU, storage, credits), node metadata, and a reference to the node’s own ADM API.

Any ADM implementation could extend the list of Allocations.

2.2.3 Deployments

A Deployment represents the execution of an application blueprint on a selected allocation. Deployments are asynchronous, meaning the ADM service returns immediately and the caller must poll for updates. A Deployment links:

- application: the blueprint to deploy
- allocation: where it will be deployed
- inputs: property list passed to parameterize the template

Additionally, when getting a deployment, the response contains additional information:

- status: The current state of the deployment. Values include:
 - unknown: Status cannot be determined.
 - pending: Request accepted, waiting to start.
 - running: Deployment is currently running.
 - stopped: Deployment was stopped or paused.
 - off: Resources are powered off or inactive.
 - failed: Deployment finished with an error.
 - configured: The deployment is running, and the configuration was successfully applied.
 - unconfigured: Configuration failed to apply, but the deployment is still running.
 - deleting: Deletion is in progress.
 - deleted: Deployment was deleted.
- details: A free-text description providing more context about the current status. This may include reasons for failure, the current workflow step, or backend-specific hints.
- outputs: A list of key/value pairs representing the output parameters of the application blueprint. These are typically runtime-generated values, such as the endpoint to access the application, access credentials, etc.

2.2.3.1 Estimate deployment resources

The deployments endpoint also enables retrieving the number of resources required by a particular application. Setting the *dryRun* parameter to 'true', the deployment will not be made, and a JSON structure will be returned with the number of resources needed, together with the user quotas in the particular allocation selected.

2.2.4 Paging

Paging in an API is required to limit the amount of data returned in a single response, improving performance, reducing memory and network load. All list endpoints return a Page:

- from, limit, count
- prevPage, nextPage
- elements (typed per resource: allocations, applications, deployments)

2.3 Endpoints overview

2.3.1 Endpoint /allocations

Method	Description
GET	List user-visible allocations
POST	Register/record an allocation
GET /allocation/{id}	Get allocation details
PUT /allocation/{id}	Update an existing allocation
DELETE /allocation/{id}	Remove an allocation

Table 1 – Allocation endpoints

2.3.2 Endpoint /applications

Method	Description
GET	List application blueprints
GET /application/{id}?version=	Get detailed blueprint info

Table 2 – Applications endpoints

2.3.3 Endpoint /deployments

Method	Description
GET	List existing deployments
POST	Start a new deployment
POST /deployments/?dryRun=true	Estimate the amount of resources
GET /deployment/{id}	Retrieve status/details
DELETE /deployment/{id}	Request a teardown of a deployment

Table 3 – Deployments endpoints

2.3.3.1 Deployment flow

Create Deployment

POST /deployments

Returns:

- 202 Accepted and a DeploymentId

indicating the deployment has been queued.

Client must poll the resource until it reaches the “configured” state.

Get Deployment Status

```
GET /deployment/{deploymentId}
```

Returns:

- A full DeploymentInfo object including the state, details and outputs.

Delete Deployment

```
DELETE /deployment/{deploymentId}
```

Returns:

- 202 Accepted, meaning teardown has been requested

Client must poll the resource until deleted

2.3.4 Endpoint /version

Returns the service version.

3 Response to Community Need

Cloud infrastructures provide suitable platforms for meeting the computational demands of scientific applications. They allow users to tailor the execution environment to their specific needs using Virtual Machines (VMs) or containers. However, leveraging public or on-premises Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) clouds often requires advanced system administration skills. The ADM capability for an EOSC node aims to facilitate application deployment through a standardised API for accessing compute and storage resources offered by the EOSC Nodes, typically via IaaS clouds such as OpenStack.

4 High-Level Service Architecture

Figure 2 provides a high-level view of the ADM reference implementation of the ADM capability based on the Infrastructure Manager (ADIM) [4]. The ADIM service relies on the IM to perform the actual deployments in the cloud platforms. For allocations, it can use a database backend (SQLite, MySQL, or MongoDB) if no private value needs to be stored (e.g., using OIDC tokens), or HashiCorp Vault if some allocations store private credentials as passwords or secret values. Finally, for applications, two backends are supported: a GitHub repository of TOSCA templates (as in [5]) to retrieve the list of TOSCA files in a particular folder, or the EOSC Beyond Service Catalogue [6] to retrieve the list of available Deployable Applications.

Figure 2. ADIM High level architecture

5 Definitions

Acronym	Definition
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ADM	Application Deployment Manager
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
VM	Virtual Machine
ADIM	Application Deployment with Infrastructure Manager
IM	Infrastructure Manager

Table 4 - Definitions

6 Related Guidelines

This table indicates the guidelines related to the guidelines being described in this document.

Resource Type	Title	Link
Service	Service Catalogue: Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines	https://zenodo.org/records/8375323
Service	Interoperability Guideline for TOSCA Deployable Services	https://zenodo.org/records/17649143

Table 5 – Related Guidelines

7 Adopted Standards

The following table describes the main standards, protocols, APIs, etc. adopted by the Deployment Service, intended for interoperability or integration with the service.

Resource Type	Title	Short Description	relatedIdentifier
Standard	OpenAPI 3.1	The ADM API is compatible with the OpenAPI standard.	https://spec.openapis.org/oas/v3.1.0.html
Standard	TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.0	TOSCA version 1.0 specification is a YAML rendering which is intended to simplify the authoring of TOSCA service templates.	https://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML/v1.0/csprd01/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML-v1.0-csprd01.html

Table 6 – Adopted Standards

8 Integration Options

This guideline describes the different integration models supported by the ADM API and how external services or platforms can interact with EOSC resources.

In all integration scenarios, EOSC AAI authentication is mandatory, since all protected endpoints require a valid OIDC Bearer token issued by the EOSC Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure.

Figure 3. ADM Integration options

8.1 Deploy on resources of the same node

This integration allows a service, workflow engine, or platform to deploy workloads directly on the resources hosted by the same EOSC node that offers the ADM capability, that is, exposes the ADM API.

Key characteristics:

- No federation calls are needed; the allocation and deployment operations stay local to the node.
- The client only needs to discover the node's available Allocations, Applications, and submit Deployments using the same ADM endpoint.
- This is the simplest and most direct integration path.

Use this option when:

- The platform is tightly integrated with a specific node.
- You want to minimize cross-node communication.
- You rely exclusively on the node's internal resource offerings.

8.2 Deploy on resources of the same node

This integration allows a system to deploy workloads to a different EOSC node than the one exposing the ADM API that the user interacts with.

Supported by the federation model:

- Allocation discovery may span multiple nodes.
- Each EOSC node provides its own ADM API endpoint inside EoscNodeEnvironment; clients can follow this link to deploy applications on other EOSC node computing resources.
- Credential delegation via EOSC AAI is essential so the remote node can authorize and deploy the requested application.
- Application templates may be hosted on another node's ADM and will have a reference to the ADM service from which they can be retrieved.

8.3 Deploy on Cloud resources accessible by the user

This integration allows deployments to run on user-provided environments, outside the EOSC-managed nodes, such as:

- Private OpenStack tenants
- Private Kubernetes clusters

The user registers these environments through the POST /allocations endpoint using OpenStackEnvironment or KubernetesEnvironment, including:

- Hostname or API endpoint
- Credentials or access tokens
- Optional parameters such as region, project, or domain

9 Interoperability Guidelines

Please note that the Interoperability Guidelines are not intended to replace manuals or implementation documentation, but to summarize what is required to maintain compatibility across the EOSC federation.

9.1 Deploy on resources of the same node

This integration allows:

- Direct, straightforward interoperability, since clients interact with a single ADM API endpoint.
- Predictable resource behavior, as all deployments, blueprint resolution, and environment information come from the same node.

9.2 Deploy on resources on other EOSC node

This integration allows:

- True multi-node execution.
- Transparent access to remote resources from a single entry point.
- Complex workflows orchestrating resources from various providers.

9.3 Deploy on Cloud resources accessible by the user

This integration allows:

- Interoperability with external, user-managed infrastructures using the ADM API as a unified orchestration layer.
- A consistent API for deployments regardless of backend ownership.
- Hybrid deployments mixing EOSC and user-owned infrastructure.
- Advanced users can integrate their own infrastructure into EOSC workflows.

10 Automated Compliance Testing

To support interoperability and ensure that services correctly implement the ADM API specification, a suite of Robot Framework tests has been developed [7]. These tests automatically validate whether an endpoint behaves according to the formal OpenAPI schema, including request/response structures, authentication requirements, pagination behavior, and error-handling semantics. By running this test suite against an ADM-compatible service, developers can quickly detect deviations from the official specification and verify full compliance before integrating their service into the EOSC federation. This automated approach significantly reduces validation effort and provides a consistent, reproducible method for assessing conformance.

References

- [1] Miguel Caballer, Germán Moltó, Amanda Calatrava and Ignacio Blanquer. "Infrastructure Manager: A TOSCA-Based Orchestrator for the Computing Continuum". Journal of Grid Computing, Volume 21, Issue 3, 2023, DOI: [10.1007/s10723-023-09686-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10723-023-09686-7).
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- [3] EOSC Application Deployment Manager API Specification: <https://github.com/EGI-Federation/eosc-application-deployment-manager>
- [4] Application Deployment with Infrastructure Manager: <https://github.com/grycap/adim/>
- [5] TOSCA Templates: <https://github.com/grycap/tosca/tree/main/templates>
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- [7] EOSC Application Deployment Manager API Compliance Tests with the Robot Framework: <https://github.com/grycap/adm-compliance-tests>